

The Isomeric Transformation of *allo*-Cinnamylidene Acetic Acid into the Normal Form with Iodine as Photo-catalyst, in Methyl Alcohol Solution.

Part II.

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Liebermann discovered that *allocinnamylidene acetic acid* is very slowly transformed into the normal form under the influence of light, but in presence of iodine this photochemical transformation is very rapid (*Ber.*, 1895, 28, 1446). In a previous paper by Ghosh and Gupta the velocity of the above transformation in chloroform solution has been studied (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 2, 241). In the present paper the results obtained with methyl alcohol as solvent are given.

The method for the estimation of the quantity of *allo*-form which has been changed into the normal form as described in the previous paper had to be considerably modified in this case. The following experimental procedure was finally adopted: 2 c. c. of the alcohol solution containing the *allo*-acid were taken out and poured into a small stoppered conical flask containing perfectly anhydrous sodium thiosulphate. The iodine immediately reacted with sodium thiosulphate and the

solution became colourless. The flask was then introduced into a vacuum desiccator connected with an oil-pump of large capacity. The alcohol evaporated rapidly at a temperature somewhat below 30° and the *allo*-acid during this process of evaporation did not undergo any further transformation into the normal form. Three c. c. of dry benzene was then added and shaken vigorously to dissolve the acids in the solid residue. The benzene solution was then poured into a long stoppered tube and kept overnight in a thermostat. One c. c. of the clear liquid was sucked up by a pipette through a plug of glass wool fitted at its lower end and titrated with baryta solution. The *allo*-acid is freely soluble in benzene but the normal acid is only slightly soluble. Table I gives the solubility of the normal acid in benzene at different temperatures in gram moles per c. c.

TABLE I.

Temperature.	Solubility $\times 10^5$
15°	24.5
22°	30.4
30°	44.4
35°	57.5

From the solubility curve of normal acid in benzene, the quantity of normal acid at the temperature of the thermostat was determined and the difference between the total quantity of acid in 1 c. c. of benzene and the solubility of normal acid gave the amount of *allo*-acid in the solid residue of the conical flask which has dissolved in one c. c. of benzene. The total *allo*-acid in the residue is three times this quantity and was present in 2 c. c. of the alcohol solution.

The experimental arrangement is essentially the same as given in the previous paper. A hundred candle power point-o-lite lamp was used as the source of light and convex lenses of different focal lengths were used to obtain parallel beams of light of varying intensity. The light was passed through a filter of copper sulphate solution 10 cm. thick to cut off heat radiations and then entered the reaction vessel ($4 \times 4 \times 1$ cm.) enclosed in a double jacketed copper box with a glass window to admit light. This copper box was maintained at constant temperature by circulating water from a thermostat. The intensity of incident radiation and the fraction of incident light absorbed by the reacting solution was measured by a Moll thermopile and galvanometer calibrated by means of a Hefner lamp.

The End-point of Reaction.—It was found that the transformation of *allo*-acid into the normal form does not proceed to completion in methyl alcohol solution. The reaction stops after ninety per cent. of the *allo*-acid has been converted into the normal variety. This percentage conversion was found to be independent of (1) concentration of iodine, (2) the intensity of incident light, and (3) almost independent of temperature. Such behaviour is indeed expected if both iodine and light act simply as catalysts. The negligible effect of temperature on the percentage conversion at equilibrium is to be ascribed to the fact that the energy change in this transformation is very small. The exact value of the heat of transformation in this case is not known, but for the corresponding change of *allo*-furfuraldehyde acrylic acid into the normal form the heat of transformation is only 4.3 calories (Roloff, *Zeit. physikal. Chem.*, 1898, 26, 337).

The simple equation, $k = \frac{1}{t_2 - t_1} \cdot \log \frac{a}{a-x}$ for the velocity

of a monomolecular reaction cannot be applied to this case. We have rather to use the more complicated equation for homogeneous unimolecular opposing reaction

$$k = k_1 \frac{a}{z} = \frac{1}{t_2 - t_1} \cdot \log \frac{z}{z - x_1}$$

where a is the initial concentration of *allo*-acid, z is the concentration of normal acid at equilibrium, and x is the quantity of *allo*-acid converted into normal form in time t ; in the following tables

$$k' = \frac{1}{t} \log \frac{z}{z-x} \quad \text{and} \quad k'' = \frac{1}{t_2 - t_1} \cdot \log \frac{z - x_1}{z - x_2}$$

TABLE II.

Solvent—*Methyl alcohol*.

$I_0 = 133/138$ Hefner⁵: Initial concentration of *allo*-acid, 0.2794 *N*.

Temp. = 32°: Concentration of iodine = 0.001 *N*.

Time.	C. c. baryta solution equivalent to		k'	k''
	conc. of <i>allo</i> -acid + dissolved normal acid.	conc. of <i>allo</i> - acid.		
0 0	50.8	50.8
t_1 80	49.66	39.16	.0037	...
t_2 110	43.28	32.78	.0046	.0069
t_3 140	37.39	26.89	.0053	.0074
t_4 174	32.92	22.42	.0069	.0074
			Mean .0072	

TABLE III.

Concentration of iodine = 0.00202 N.

Time.	Concentration of <i>allo</i> -acid in c. c. baryta solution.	k'	k''
0	57.87
45	36.27	.0119
75	23.86	.0141	.0174
100	17.51	.0149	.0173
120	14.13	.0153	.0173
			Mean .0173

TABLE IV.

Concentration of iodine = 0.006 N.

Time.	Concentration of <i>allo</i> -acid in c.c. baryta solution.	k	k''
0	60.88
21	37.03	.0271
30	25.17	.0351	.0536
46	14.36	.0411	.0527
61	9.63	.0449	.0541
75	7.81	.0460	.0534
			Mean .0535

TABLE V.

Concentration of iodine = 0.01179 N.

Time.	Concentration of <i>allo</i> -acid in c.c. baryta solution.	k'	k''
0	58.09
16	39.80	.0269
25	24.85	.0416	.0674
35	14.90	.0499	.0692
45	10.27	.0557	.0699
			Mean .0686

TABLE VI.

Concentration of iodine = 0.0155 N.

Time.	Concentration of <i>allo</i> -acid in c.c. baryta solution	k'	k''
0	47.32
13	32.70	.0322
23	20.17	.0442	.0593
33	13.78	.0469	.0564
43	9.82	.0495	.0568
53	7.48	.0520	.0580
			Mean .0576

TABLE VII.

Concentration of iodine = 0.024 N.

Time.	Concentration of <i>allo-acid</i> in c. c. baryta solution.	k'	k''
0	22.6
17	14.71	.0288
32	9.76	.0311	.0338
47	6.71	.0322	.0343
62	4.83	.0334	.0350
84	3.69	.0315	.0322
			Mean .0338

TABLE VIII.

Concentration of iodine = 0.0320 N.

Time.	Concentration of <i>allo-acid</i> in c.c. baryta solution.	k'	k''
0	83.1
20	55.07	.0236
35	39.44	.0251	.0269
50	32.10	.0229	.0225
65	25.87	.0223	.0218
80	23.34	.0200	.0189
			Mean .0225

TABLE IX.

Concentration of iodine = 0.048 *N*.

Time.	Concentration of <i>allo-acid</i> in c. c. baryta solution.	<i>k'</i>	<i>k''</i>
0	83.1
20	66.5	.0121	...
35	55.5	.0131	.0146
50	47.5	.0124	.0134
70	41.5	.0115	.0114
			Mean .0131

It will be noticed from Tables II-IX that for smaller concentrations of the catalyst iodine, the const. *k'* continually increased indicating that in these experiments the reaction passes through a period of induction. As, however, the concentration of iodine increased to 0.024 *N* the induction period disappeared and identical values of velocity constant were obtained from the beginning of the reaction. That there is this disturbance at the beginning of the reaction is also evident from the fact that the values of *k''*, calculated from data obtained after some time has elapsed after exposure to light, are all identical within the limits of experimental error. The variation of the velocity constant *k''*, with the concentration of iodine is given in diagram I (*a*). It will be noticed that the constant increases very rapidly as the concentration of iodine increases, passes through a maximum and then diminishes. This point will be further discussed later on.

It is important to mention here that the above data were obtained by exposing to light a mixture of freshly prepared solutions of *allo-acid* and iodine in methyl alcohol.

FIG. I.

The Effect of 'ageing' of the Solutions on the Velocity Constants.

In course of performing the experiments recorded above it was noticed that the results obtained were not always concordant. This puzzling phenomenon was ultimately traced to the effect of the 'ageing' of the solutions of the *allo*-acid and iodine. It was found that if the reaction was started by mixing and exposing to light the methyl alcohol solutions of iodine and *allo*-acid immediately after they were separately made, the velocity constants obtained under identical conditions of concentration, temperature and light intensity were always the same. But if old solutions are mixed together and exposed to light the values of velocity constants were always less.

Initial conc. of *allo*-acid, $14.23 \times 10^{-2} N$.

Concentration of iodine, $1.5 \times 10^{-2} N$.

Light intensity, 133/138 Hefner.

Temperature, 32° .

TABLE X.

Solutions mixed and exposed to light 30 min. after preparation.

Time.	Conc. of <i>allo</i> -acid in c.c. baryta solution.	k'	k''
0	41.52
15	26.26	.0850
25	14.83	.0499	.0727
35	9.56	.0552	.0704
45	6.82	.0587	.0704
			Mean .0712

TABLE XI.

Solutions mixed and exposed to light 22 hours after preparation.

Time.	Conc. of <i>allo</i> -acid in c.c. baryta solution.	k'	k''
0	41.68
16	23.96	·0342
26	16.50	·0428	·0474
36	12.03	·0435	·0462
46	8.95	·0449	·0474
56	7.17	·0451	·0472
			Mean ·0471

TABLE XII.

Solutions mixed and exposed to light $44\frac{1}{2}$ hours after preparation.

Time.	Conc. of <i>allo</i> -acid in c.c. baryta solution.	k'	k''
0	41.91
18	23.06	·0373
28	16.84	·0382	·0396
38	12.79	·0382	·0391
48	9.57	·0400	·0409
58	7.78	·0400	·0409
			Mean ·0401

FIG. II.

TABLE XIII.

Solution mixed and exposed to light $68\frac{3}{4}$ hours after preparation.

Time.	Conc. of <i>allo-acid</i> in c. c baryta solution.	k'	k''
0	41.98
20	24.27	.0315
38	13.88	.0359	.0391
51	10.21	.0361	.0391
60	8.47	.0366	.0386
			Mean .0389

It will be seen that the values of k'' are identical for the same experiment, but vary with the ageing of the solution. The results are plotted in Fig. II. k'' diminishes with time in an asymptotic way, its value after a certain time becoming more or less constant. It will be further noticed that the values of k' as noted before are different for the same experiment for freshly prepared solutions. But with the ageing of the solutions, the values of k' become identical indicating that the disturbing influences which were responsible for the induction period have disappeared. The nature of these disturbing influences is not clear at present.

Effect of Initial Concentration of the allo-Acid on the Velocity of Reaction.

It was noticed in a previous paper by Ghosh and Gupta (*loc. cit.*) that other conditions being the same, the monomolecular velocity coefficient in chloroform solutions diminishes with increase in the initial concentration

of the *allo*-acid. Similar results have been obtained with methyl alcohol as solvent, as will be clear from the Table XIV and curve I(b) where the results are given diagrammatically.

TABLE XIV.

Initial concentration of *allo*-acid, $14.23 \times 10^{-2} N$.
Temp. = 32° . Intensity = 133/138 Hefner.

Concentration of iodine.	$\cdot 0027N$	$\cdot 0053N$	$\cdot 01066N$	$\cdot 0212N$	$\cdot 032N$	$\cdot 044N$	$\cdot 0543N$
Velocity coefficient, k'' .	$\cdot 0316$	$\cdot 0549$	$\cdot 0798$	$\cdot 0547$	$\cdot 0362$	$\cdot 0268$	$\cdot 0218$

It will be noticed that the curve I (b) remains parallel to curve I(a) and is always *above* it.

Influence of Temperature on the Velocity of Reaction.

It has been pointed out before that the percentage of conversion of the *allo*-acid into normal form, when equilibrium was reached, did not vary perceptibly with temperature. The influence of temperature on velocity coefficient was also quite small.

TABLE XV.

Temp. = 38° , Intensity = 133/138 Hefner.

Initial conc. of *allo*-acid = $14.23 \times 10^{-2} N$.

Conc. of iodine.	$\cdot 00164N$	$\cdot 0054N$	$\cdot 0211N$	$\cdot 0311N$	$\cdot 0422N$
Velocity coefficient, k''	$\cdot 0218$	$\cdot 0611$	$\cdot 0613$	$\cdot 0404$	$\cdot 0304$

The results are given in curve I (c).

The Influence of Incident Light on the Velocity of Transformation.

TABLE XVI.

Initial conc. of *allo*-acid = $14.23 \times 10^{-2} N$.

$I_0 = 32/138$ Hefner. Temp. = 38°

Conc. of iodine.	·0062N.	·0106N.	·0190N.	·0248N.	·03816N.
Velocity coefficient, k''	·0130	·023	·0186	·0130	·0075

The results are graphically represented in curve I (d).

TABLE XVII.

Initial conc. of *allo*-acid = $14.23 \times 10^{-2} N$;

$I_0 = 25/138$ Hefner ; Temp. = 38° .

Conc. of iodine	·00878N.	·01756N.
Velocity coefficient, k''	·0154	·0160

In Table XVIII are given the values of velocity coefficients for different intensities of incident radiation, other experimental conditions remaining the same.

TABLE XVIII.

Initial concentration of *allo*-acid, 1.423×10^{-2} *N*.
Temperature, 38°.

Conc. of iodine.	Ratios of intensities.	Ratios of velocity coefficient.
.00878 <i>N</i>	32/35 = 1.28	.0196/.0154 = 1.27
.1756 <i>N</i>	32/25 = 1.28	.02/.016 = 1.25
.020 <i>N</i>	133/32 = 4.16	.0336/.0176 = 3.61
.0248 <i>N</i>	133/32 = 4.16	.616/.0130 = 3.97
.030 <i>N</i>	133/32 = 4.16	.0420/.0104 = 4.04
.038 <i>N</i>	133/32 = 4.16	.0332/.0075 = 4.43

It will be seen that the ratio of the velocity coefficients is approximately proportional to the ratio of incident intensities.

Estimation of the Number of Molecules of allo-acid transformed per Quantum of Light absorbed.

In chloroform solution, one quantum of light absorbed by iodine transformed under different conditions of experiment between 1 to 2.8 molecules of *allo*-acid. In methyl alcohol solution, the reaction is far more sensitive to light. That the velocity coefficients are practically independent of temperature and proportional to the intensity of incident radiation suggests that the mechanism of reaction may be a simple one. The fact that the velocity coefficient passes through a maximum with increase in iodine concentration, whereas the amount of absorbed light steadily increases as the concentration of iodine increases at once indicates that

Einstein's law of the photo-chemical equivalent in its simplest form is not applicable to this reaction. The following calculation indicates the number of molecules transformed by one quantum of light under different experimental conditions. Radiant energy from a Hefner lamp at a distance of 1 metre whose intensity is equal to 900 ergs per square per cm. sec. produced a galvanometer deflection of 138 divisions. The light absorbed by 0.001*N* iodine is equivalent to 17 divisions of the galvanometer. Hence

$$\text{energy absorbed} = \frac{17 \times 900}{138} \text{ ergs.}$$

Assuming the mean wave-length of efficient light to be 500 $\mu\mu$, $h\nu$ becomes equal to 3.9×10^{-12} ergs. Therefore the number of quanta in the absorbed light = 28.4×10^{12} quanta.

The change of *allo*-acid in 30 min. (see Table II) in $2/3$ c.c. of the solution corresponding to a surface of $2/3$ sq. cm. = 6.38 c.c. of 0.003665 *N* alkali.

Therefore the number of molecules transformed per sq. cm. of surface \times thickness of 1 cm. per sec.

$$= \frac{6.38 \times 0.003665 \times 3 \times 6.16 \times 10^{23}}{30 \times 60 \times 1000 \times 2} = 12 \times 10^{16}$$

Therefore, the number of molecules divided by the number of quanta = 4.23×10^2 .

Results of the same order were obtained with different concentrations of iodine.

It rarely happens that the velocity coefficients pass through a maximum as the concentration of photo-catalyst increases. This peculiarity of the solvent action of methyl alcohol was also noticed by Soulan in the relative change in the conductivity of a fluorescent

solution of esculine on illumination. Here too, for the same intensity of illumination, the relative change in the conductivity passes through a maximum as the concentration of esculine in methyl alcohol increases (*vide* Rule, *Phil. Mag.*, 1926, 1, 538). Similar phenomena are observed in the production of phosphorescence where the intensity of phosphorescence passes through a maximum as the concentration of the active substance in the solid solution increases (Meritt, *Physical Review*, 1915, 5, 319). Recently Rule (*loc. cit.*) has also observed a similar maximum in the curve representing the variation of the E. M. F. of a photo-active cell prepared from a solution of a fluorescent dye, with the concentration of that dye. Perrin (*Compt. rend.* 1923, 177, 469) has shown that if the concentration of a fluorescent solution is increased, beginning at zero, the fluorescence begins to increase, passes through a maximum and then decreases as the concentration is further increased.

The Elementary Phenomenon of Photo-catalysis by Iodine.

The photo-catalyst molecule of iodine absorbs a quantum of radiation and passes into the excited state. It might revert (1) to the normal stable condition by re-emitting the above quantum of radiation, (2) to another stable condition by emitting a quantum of different radiation, which we call fluorescent radiation, or it might revert to its normal state by colliding with a molecule of *allo*-acid and communicating in that process, its energy of excitation to the *allo*-acid molecules which in their turn under the impulse of this increased energy, become ultimately transformed into the normal acid molecules. The rate of transformation will therefore

be proportional to the concentration of the active iodine molecules and the molecules of the *allo*-acid. The monomolecular velocity constant with respect to *allo*-acid is therefore a measure of the concentration of active iodine molecules under the conditions of experiment. Now Perrin assumes (*Compt. rend.*, 1924, 178, 1978) that in strong solutions the molecules of the fluorescent body are protected by each other and he suggests the following mechanism (*vide* Rule, *loc. cit.*).

As the concentration increases the amount of light absorbed increases, and hence the number of molecules activated increases until a concentration is reached, when the whole of the effective incident radiation is absorbed. Beyond this point the number of activated molecules cannot increase and should have a constant value but for the protective action of one molecule on another. It may be supposed that a molecule, capable of being brought to an excited condition by the absorption of radiation, takes a certain finite time to attain its new configuration. Now if during this time a second molecule of the same nature approaches near the first, it can acquire, by resonance, part of the energy of the first and so disturb its excited condition. When the solution is dilute the protective action of the molecules over each other is small as the mean distance between the molecules is large; but with increase in concentration the mean distance diminishes and this protective influence plays a more and more important part until the point is reached, where the increase in the number of active molecules due to the mere fact of increase in concentration and hence absorption of light, is compensated for by the reduction in the number of molecules in the requisite excited state due to this protective influence. Beyond this point the reduction in the number of molecules on account of the protective influence is increasingly greater than the

increase in the number of active molecules resulting in increased absorption of light. The maximum point on the velocity constant - iodine concentration curve and the subsequent falling off in the value of the velocity constant are thus explained.

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